

NANOFACTS

Grant Agreement (GA) No. 952259

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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities during the past 13 months of the **NANOFACTS** project. We have joined forces with our partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland, The School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, to implement the best dissemination strategies.

The conditions of COVID-19 outbreak led to significant shifting of the manner of communication and dissemination toward the virtual world. In order to boost our online presence, we have made particular attention to designing effective dissemination through our Website and Social media platforms. In addition, whenever possible we used other online dissemination channels, such as online meetings, virtual events, etc.

Addressing a wide spectrum of target groups was extremely challenging, especially in the COVID-19 times. But we made sure that tailor-made messages that suit the specific target groups were crafted, addressing the scientific community, industry (in particular pharmaceutical companies) and potential users (patients), to create positive impacts in science, industrial leadership and employability, and to help enhance the excellence of cancer research in Serbia, as well as the rest of Europe. On the other hand, the dissemination targeted students with the aim to endorse their specialization in this topic and ensure the critical mass of prominent researchers that will contribute to the development of the knowledge-based society. Patients were another crucial target group, since the improvement of their understanding of cancer research-related science may improve their readiness to undertake newly approved clinical treatment practices and procedures, while allowing researchers to better understand patients' interests and priorities. General public needed to be well informed about the latest cancer-related research directions and potentials for improvement of current practices.

Due to COVID19 outbreak, all the activities were carried out in accordance with health and safety measures.

Another outcome of the Covid-19 pandemic conditions is that the main dissemination event of the project (Training school) was postponed until July 2022, with permission from the Project officer. Therefore, a large portion of dissemination activities, including printed materials, face-to-face meetings and in person presentation events to larger audience was postponed.

In this report, the following segments are presented in detail: website traffic, social media activity, scientific publications, as well as dissemination events attended or organized by BIOS staff, engaging national and European community.

The implementation of dissemination overview gives a detailed description of the main dissemination activities. The news about the **NANOFACTS** project were spread through the official web portal, social media platforms, and dissemination events.

2. Report on Dissemination Tools and Activities

Table 1: Overview of NANOFACTS dissemination activities

Amount or Date	Activity	
15 470	Number of unique views of NANOFACTS website	Overall
5	Number of news published by NANOFACTS website	
19	Unique post published on all NANOFACTS social media accounts	
364	Followers on social media	
3	Conference publications	
7	Dissemination events	
26 May 2021	Full version (all tabs) of NANOFACTS website in English active online	
5	News published on NANOFACTS website in English	Twitter account
19	Tweets posted on NANOFACTS twitter profile in English	
21	Followers on twitter	
19	Posts published on NANOFACTS Facebook page in English	Facebook page
146	Facebook page likes	
156	Page followers	
19	Posts published on Instagram page	Instagram account
90	Followers on Instagram	
91	Followers on LinkedIn account	LinkedIn account

2.1. Electronic dissemination

2.1.1. The website

Electronic means of communication are by far the most widely spread in the 21st century and are being accessed every day by a large number of people. For this reason, they are on the top of the list of **NANOFACTS** communication channels. There are multiple subgroups of the web platforms and they are intended for different purposes.

NANOFACTS website is the first place where a person is able to find out more about the project's goals, stages, events, and personnel involved. Detailed website, presenting individual work packages, key people, illustrations representing project's overview and activities is set at www.nanofacts.net with the main purpose of illustrating the **NANOFACTS** concept and approach. The website also serve as a platform for disseminating project results to present **NANOFACTS** publications and other scientific achievements.

Figure 1: The website of the NANOFACTS project – Home page

nanofacts HOME PAGE ABOUT US PARTICIPANTS NEWS PUBLICATIONS CONTACT

BIOSENSE INSTITUTE

Novi Sad, Serbia

BioSense Institute (BIOS) coordinates, focuses and advances research, introduction and promotion of state-of-the-art solutions in agriculture, ecology, health, environmental protection, water management and industry. BioSense Institute is an internationally recognized multi-disciplinary scientific research institute and a regional provider of advanced information and communication technologies (ICT) in agriculture and environmental monitoring. Institute has a special focus on micro and nano-technology sensors, Internet of Things, Robotics, Remote Sensing and Big Data.

With state-of-the-art equipment and – most important – with an international group of more than 70 enthusiastic interdisciplinary researchers, BioSense Institute is able to perform scientific research at the global level and contribute to the development and sustainability of eco-innovation in the areas of major importance for society – agriculture, health and the environment. BioSense Institute coordinates or participates in a large number of international research projects, including 22 Horizon 2020 projects. Biosense Institute employs researchers of different backgrounds and expertise, including chemists, materials scientists, materials engineers, physicists, biologists, electronic engineers, with experience on construction and application of nanomaterials for different health, environment and agriculture-related challenges.

The **Center for sensor technologies at BIOS** focuses on the development of sensors that can detect and measure different parameters and processes in biosystems, and as such be applied to the agri-food sector, environmental monitoring, and medical applications. To address these challenging tasks, the Center brings together researchers with a range of expertise, spanning from physics, chemistry and biology to electrical engineering and materials science.

Key people:

- Dr. Nikola Knežević, Project Coordinator & WPI Leader
- Dr. Nikolina Janković, Deputy Coordinator
- Dr. Vasa Radonić, Quality Manager & WP4 Leader
- Dr. Ivana Gadjanski Stanic, WP5 Leader
- Dr. Slavica Savić, WP6 Leader
- MSc. Maša Mimica, Financial Manager
- MSc. Minja Mladenović, Dissemination Manager
- MSc. Nataša Narevski, Administrative Manager
- MSc. Milica Trajković

Figure 2: The website of the NANOFACTS project - Participants page - Consortium - BIOS Team

nanofacts HOME PAGE ABOUT US PARTICIPANTS NEWS PUBLICATIONS CONTACT

TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN

Dublin, Ireland

The **School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences of Trinity College Dublin** is based in 3 large-scale Institutes for collaborative molecular medicine and clinical research, supporting graduate education in the life sciences – with the past nine years growing focus on nanomedicine as a horizontal theme spanning the future expertise of translational medicine. The School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences is also linked to the TCD-CRANN Nanotechnology institute and TCD-AMBER centre, industrially driven hub focused in Advanced Materials and BioEngineering Research. The uniqueness of the School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences facilities is that all principal investigators share their knowledge and expertise within multiple institutes. Therefore the School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Science have unique expertise in translational research, which spans the entire spectrum from cellular based approaches, in vivo animal models to patient-orientated research.

Key people:

- Dr. Maria Jose Santos-Martinez, WP3 Leader
- Dr. Oliviero Gobbo
- Dr. Eduardo Ruiz-Hernandez

Figure 3: The website of the NANOFACTS project - Participants page - Consortium - TCD Team

A screenshot of the 'nanofacts' website's 'Participants' page for the TUW team. The page has a white background with a blue header. The 'nanofacts' logo is in the top left. A navigation menu in the top right includes 'HOME PAGE', 'ABOUT US', 'PARTICIPANTS' (with a dropdown arrow), 'NEWS', 'PUBLICATIONS', and 'CONTACT'. The main content area is titled 'THE VIENNA UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY' and 'Vienna, Austria'. A paragraph describes the 'Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics' and its focus on analytical chemistry and microfluidics. A 'Key people:' section lists four individuals: Univ. Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl (WP2 Leader), M.Sc. Florian Selinger, M.Sc. Silvia Schobesberger, and M.Sc. Ghazal Shabestanimonfared.

nanofacts HOME PAGE ABOUT US PARTICIPANTS NEWS PUBLICATIONS CONTACT

THE VIENNA UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

Vienna, Austria

The **Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics** is located within the Faculty of Chemistry and is further organized into five divisions that bridge different matters in Chemistry, Technology, Materials Science, Instrumental Analytical Chemistry, Bioanalytics, Electrochemistry and Environmental Chemistry. One scientific focus of the institute is development of analytical strategies and instrumentation including (bio)sensors, Omics-techniques, mass spectrometry, imaging techniques, ultra-trace separation and detection techniques on the elemental as well as molecular level. The latest initiative of the Faculty of Technical Chemistry is the establishment of a lab on a chip laboratory for bioscience technologies that combines aspects of microfluidics, material sciences, biosensing technologies and cell biology. Following the global trend of miniaturization, automation and integration the lab-on-a-chip laboratories maintain a range of rapid prototyping technologies and micromachining tools to develop computer controlled microanalysis platforms, biochips, micropumps and microdegassers. Furthermore, TUW and the Medical University Vienna has jointly established the Vienna Center for Engineering in Medicine (VICEM, www.vicem.at) to establish constant exchange of ideas in subject areas relevant to Health EU. We also have contact with Correlated Multimodal Imaging (CMI, www.bioimaging-austria.at), the Austrian bioimaging node initiative, and the Austrian Microfluidics Initiative (www.bionanonet.at/austrian-microfluidics-initiative), as part of the Austrian BioNanoNet.

Key people:

- Univ. Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl, WP2 Leader
- M.Sc. Florian Selinger
- M.Sc. Silvia Schobesberger.
- M.Sc. Ghazal Shabestanimonfared

Figure 4: The website of the NANOFACTS project - Participants page - Consortium - TUW Team

The website is regularly updated with the project activities, achieved results and news.

Figure 5: The website of the NANOFACTS project - Participants page - NANOFACTS Team

Figure 6. The website visitors' locations - February 19th, 2021, to December 31st, 2021.

Figure 7: The website visitors' locations - January 1st 2022 to March 3rd 2022.

Figure 8: The website statistics – February 19th 2021 to December 31st 2021.

Figure 9: The website statistics - January 1st 2022 to March 3rd 2022.

2.1.2. Social media platforms

Social media profiles on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, as well as the LinkedIn group were launched in February 2021.

We have boosted our presence on social media and all partners are using the power of social media to enhance visibility of of **NANOFACTS** project and consequently its results. Social media platforms, such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter are regularly updated.

2.1.3. Facebook page

The **NANOFACTS** project has its own Facebook page but it is constantly promoted through the BioSense Institute Facebook page also. The **NANOFACTS** Facebook page is regularly updated. The Facebook Page presents the latest results, news, and achievements of the **NANOFACTS** researchers.

Figure 10: NANOFACTS Facebook page

Key metrics:

From February 6th 2021 to March 1st 2022 the number of the followers increased to **156**.

Figure 11: Facebook page followers - February 6th 2021 - March 1st 2022

Figure 12: Facebook page likes - February 6th 2021 - March 1st 2022

Posts that had the highest number of impressions were related to extended stay visits of **NANOFACTS** researcher, e.g. first secondment dissemination, face-to-face meeting with Consortium members to discuss future secondments, etc. But also, posts related to different achievements of **NANOFACTS** researchers.

Figure 13: Facebook posts with highest number of impressions – First secondment dissemination

Figure 14: Facebook posts with highest number of impressions – Internal face-to-face meeting of Consortium

Figure 15: Facebook posts with highest number of impressions – Researchers attending scientific conference

Figure 16: NANOFACTS project dissemination through BioSense Institute Facebook page

2.1.4. Instagram page

The Instagram account of **NANOFACTS** project is primarily intended to reach younger audience. Instagram posts are more focused on the promotion of activities conducted by researchers involved in the project. The **NANOFACTS** Instagram page is regularly updated with the latest results, news, and achievements of the **NANOFACTS** researchers.

Figure 17: NANOFACTS Instagram account

Figure 18: Instagram posts with highest number of impressions – Posts related to successful first secondment

Figure 19: Instagram posts with highest number of impressions – First training on first secondment

Figure 20: Instagram posts with highest number of impressions – Meeting dedicated to first secondment, where young researchers presented their results

Figure 21: Reach, Likes and Impressions on NANOFATCS Instagram account

2.1.5. LinkedIn account

The **NANOFACTS** project has its own LinkedIn account but account of the BioSense Institute is also used in the most efficient way to make a bigger impact and to disseminate the **NANOFACTS** project activities and progress. The content is offered in English.

Figure 22: NANOFATCS LinkedIn account

Key metrics:

From February 6th 2021 to March 1st 2022 the number of followers reached is **91**.

Figure 23: NANOFACETS LinkedIn account – Impressions’ metrics

Figure 24: NANOFACETS LinkedIn account – Reactions’ metrics

Figure 25: NANOFACETS LinkedIn account – Engagement rate

Update engagement ⓘ Time range: Feb 28, 2021 - Feb 28, 2022 ▾ Show: 20 ▾

Update title	Post type	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions	Comments	Shares	Follows
<p>🔔 The first secondment is in progress! Our #youngresearchers are on their extended... Posted by Minja Mladenovic 10/7/2021</p>	Image	All followers	1,651	-	587	35.55%	29	0	0	-
<p>Our young researchers attended IEEE Authorship and Open Access... Posted by Minja Mladenovic 10/1/2021</p>	Image	All followers	324	-	66	20.37%	13	0	0	-
<p>📅 Yesterday, we had a #meeting dedicated to the 1st secondment, where o... Posted by Minja Mladenovic 12/10/2021</p>	Image	All followers	576	-	43	7.47%	13	0	0	-

Figure 26: NANOFACTS LinkedIn Account – List of top posts

Most of our followers belong to the following communities: **Research, Education, Engineering, Business, and Media and Communication.**

Figure 27: NANOFACTS LinkedIn Account – Followers Demographics

Figure 28: NANOFACTS project dissemination through BioSense Institute LinkedIn account

2.1.6. Twitter account

The Twitter account is one of the primary tools in spreading the news about the activities related to the **NANOFACTS** project and achieved results. The account is updated regularly in English. The **NANOFACTS** project has its own Twitter account but it is constantly promoted through the BioSense Institute Twitter account also.

Figure 29: NANOFACTS Twitter account

Key metrics:

From the launch of the account, during the past 13 months, the average number of tweet impressions per month was around **300**.

The following figures present the Twitter analytics for some of the most active months: October 2021, November 2021 and December 2021.

The pictures provide an overview of the number of Tweets, total Tweet impressions, profile visits, mentions, and the number of new followers.

Oct 2021 • 31 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 313 impressions

The 1st secondment is in progress! Our [#youngresearchers](#) are on their [#extendedstayvisits](#) at [@tu_wien](#). The 1st training has been dedicated to glass preparation for the fabrication of microfluidic chips. Dear students, work hard and have fun! We are so proud of you!

[#nanofacts](#) <pic.twitter.com/CmjhEuJ2HD>

2 replies 6 likes

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top mention earned 29 engagements

Our [@NANOFACTS2](#) team on the extended visit at the [@tu_wien](#) working on the development of microfluidic chips for use in biosensing. [#Horizon2020](#) [#ResearchImpactEU](#) <pic.twitter.com/wdegdkMGQI>

1 reply 12 likes

View Tweet

OCT 2021 SUMMARY

Tweets	3	Tweet impressions	693
Profile visits	62	Mentions	1
New followers	3		

Figure 30: NANOFACTS Twitter Account – October 2021 Analytics

Nov 2021 • 30 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 156 impressions

[#NANOFACTS](#) team member [@MinjaMladenovic](#) from [@BioSenseRS](#) attended the 7th [#NanoTodayConference](#) presenting her research. Within the conference, she also attended the Nano Today Author [#workshop](#).

[#h2020](#) [#horizon](#) [#Twinning](#) [#conference](#) [#research](#) [#science](#) <pic.twitter.com/8ttbk71E57>

1 reply 4 likes

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top media Tweet earned 16 impressions

[#NANOFACTS](#) team member from [@tcddublin](#), Dr. Oliviero Gobbo, has published a review article.

To find out more visit [!!! mdpi.com/2079-4991/11/1...](http://mdpi.com/2079-4991/11/1...)

[#horizon2020](#) [#twinning](#) [#science](#) [#article](#) [#nanotheranostic](#) <pic.twitter.com/usPpYiqiSh>

4 likes

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

NOV 2021 SUMMARY

Tweets	1	Tweet impressions	364
Profile visits	151	New followers	1

Figure 31: NANOFACTS Twitter Account – November 2021 Analytics

Dec 2021 • 31 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 84 impressions

Yesterday, we had a **#meeting** dedicated to the 1st secondment, where our young researchers presented their **#experience** and results. We are all thankful to have such devoted students and to have a chance to learn from their experiences.

#nanofacts #twinning #H2020 #team pic.twitter.com/8nwgTIsPbc

1

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top media Tweet earned 51 impressions

#NANOFACTS team members from **@BioSenseRS** participated in the Congress of the Serbian Association for Cancer Research. It was useful to hear more about the translational potential of **#CancerResearch** in Serbia. We hope that our project will contribute to this topic in the future. pic.twitter.com/4iP339Fomx

1 5

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

DEC 2021 SUMMARY

Tweets	4	Tweet impressions	330
Profile visits	12	New followers	1

Figure 32: NANOFACTS Twitter Account – December 2021 Analytics

BioSense Institute @BioSenseRS · Jun 8, 2021
Today is the **#WorldBrainTumorDay**. Our project **@NANOFACTS2** is enhancing the capabilities of **#BioSense** regarding research in cancer theranostics nanomaterials and biosensing diagnostics of cancer! We are glad that we can contribute and raise awareness! **@EU_H2020 #ResearchImpactEU**

BioSense Institute @BioSenseRS · Jan 29, 2021
So excited for the **#NANOFACTS** project kick off meeting! **@BioSenseRS** is partnering with the most prominent European **#scientific** institutions in order to work on nanotechnology-facilitated cancer theranostics! **@EU_H2020 #twinning #ResearchImpactEU**

BioSense Institute @BioSenseRS · Oct 29, 2021
Our **@NANOFACTS2** team on the extended visit at **@tu_wien** working on the development of microfluidic chips for use in biosensing. **#Horizon2020 #ResearchImpactEU**

Networking Activities for Nanotechnology-Facilitated Cancer Theranostics - NANOFACTS
Type of the project: Coordination and support action
Topic: #EU_H2020-01-2020 Twinning

Figure 33: NANOFACTS project dissemination through BioSense Institute Twitter account

2.2. Printed dissemination

2.2.1. Scientific publications

Scientific publishing is one of the main channels targeting academia members, researchers, and professionals in the project scope of work.

The NANOFACETS researchers have published their results in open access peer reviewed international journals and in presentations at international conferences.

The full list of scientific publications is given below:

Peer-reviewed journals:

1. Mladenović, M., Morgan, I., Ilić, N., Saoud, M., Pergal, M. V., Kaluđerović, G. N., & Knežević, N. Ž. (2021). pH-Responsive Release of Ruthenium Metallotherapeutics from Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanocarriers. *Pharmaceutics*, 13(4), 460. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics13040460>
2. Živojević, K., Mladenović, M., Djisalov, M., Mundzic, M., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., Gadjanski, I., & Knežević, N. Ž. (2021). Advanced mesoporous silica nanocarriers in cancer theranostics and gene editing applications. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 337, 193–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.07.029>
3. Lynch, M. J., & Gobbo, O. L. (2021). Advances in Non-Animal Testing Approaches towards Accelerated Clinical Translation of Novel Nanotheranostic Therapeutics for Central Nervous System Disorders. *Nanomaterials*, 11(10), 2632. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11102632>

Conference papers:

1. Nikola Knezevic, Minja Mladenovic, Mirjana Mundzic and Aleksandra Pavlovic, Stimuli-Responsive Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Applications in Cancer Theranostics, 2021 MRS Fall Meeting, Abstract Book, SB03.05.10, November 30 – December 7, 2021. Virtual event.
2. Minja Mladenovic, Mirjana Mundzic, Aleksandra Pavlovic, Nikola Knezevic, Potential of mesoporous silica nanoparticles for applications in targeted treatment of cancer, 5th Congress of the “Serbian Association for Cancer Research – SDIR” with international participation „Translational potential of cancer research in Serbia”, Abstract book, P44, December 3rd, 2021. Virtual event.
3. Minja Mladenović, Mirjana Mundžić; Aleksandra Pavlović; Nikola Knežević, Anticancer Applications of Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles, 7th Nano Today Conference, 16 – 18 November 2021. Virtual event.

2.3. Dissemination events

2.3.1. Event attendance

1. 5th Congress of the “Serbian Association for Cancer Research – SDIR”

Figure 34: NANOFACTS team members at 5th Congress of the “Serbian Association for Cancer Research – SDIR”

Staff involved: Minja Mladenović, Aleksandra Pavlović, Mirjana Mundžić, Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Online

Date: December 3rd 2021

Website: <https://www.sdir.ac.rs/en/izvestaj-o-sdir5-kongresu/>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: The Serbian Association for Cancer Research (SDIR) was founded in November 2010 at Belgrade. SDIR’s Head Office was located at the Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia. SDIR is a non-profit association, established to achieve the objectives in the field of oncology. The objectives of the association are improvement of conditions for cancer research; advanced training; organization of study members at home and abroad and organization of professional meetings to exchange scientific information.

5th Congress of the “Serbian Association for Cancer Research – SDIR” with international participation „Translational potential of cancer research in Serbia” was held on December 3, 2021 as a virtual event. Our group participated in an interactive online poster session with the poster presentation titled “Potential of Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Applications in Targeted Treatment of Cancer”. As our group’s research focuses on the development of nanostructured silica-based materials for cancer treatment, this conference was a perfect platform to present research goals and results. In addition, the conference provided first-hand information on current best practices in basic and translational cancer research.

2. 7th Nano Today Conference, Online Live and On-Demand

Figure 35: Minja Mladenović at 7th Nano Today Conference

Staff involved: Minja Mladenović

Place: Online

Date: 16 - 18 November 2021

Website: <https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/nano-today-conference>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: The 7th Nano Today Conference took place online as a live-streamed and interactive event on 16-18 November 2021. It has been organized by the Nano Today journal, the GBA National Institute for Nanotechnology Innovation (CanNano), National Center for Nanoscience and Technology (NCNST), and Elsevier in partnership with Materials Today and chaired by Nano Today Editor-in-Chief Professor Yuliang Zhao. The latest research at the multidisciplinary frontier of nanostructured materials and devices was presented at this international conference. Since our group research focuses on the development of nanostructured silica-based materials for anticancer application, this conference was a perfect platform for presenting research aims and results. Furthermore, the conference provided first-hand information about current best practices in the field referred to above. During the conference, Nano Today Author Workshop was also organized and presented by Lauren Ashby, Executive Publisher. She gave a detailed overview of the process of writing and publishing the article.

3. 2021 MRS Fall Meeting

Stimuli-responsive Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Applications in Cancer Theranostics

Nikola Ž. Knežević

BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

nknezevic@biosense.rs

Figure 36: Dr Nikola Knežević at 2021 MRS Fall Meeting

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Online

Date: November 30 – December 7 2021

Website: <https://www.mrs.org/meetings-events/fall-meetings-exhibits/2021-mrs-fall-meeting>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: 2021 MRS Fall Meeting was organized in a new hybrid format, which offered the strong, robust scientific forum, while making sure the content was accessible to the greater materials research community. The meeting showcased breakthrough materials research in both fundamental and applied areas.

Networking events, professional development opportunities and a lively exhibit of international manufacturers, suppliers and developers rounded out the enriching meeting experience that will shape the future of materials research.

Distinguished keynote lecture was held by Nobel prize winner **Sir Kostya Novoselov**, The University of Manchester. Plenary sessions at this event included lectures from a Nobel prize laureate **Sir J. Fraser Stoddart**, Northwestern University, **Paul Alivisatos**, University of California, Berkeley, Darío Gil, IBM T. J. Watson Research Center, John A. Rogers, Northwestern University and Sharon C. Glotzer, University of Michigan.

PI of NANOFACETS, Dr Nikola Knežević, presented the research results on the topic: “Stimuli-Responsive Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Applications in Cancer Theranostics”.

4. IEEE Sensors 2021

Figure 37: Virtual attendance of Dr Slavica Savić on Dr Sohini Kar Narayan plenary lecture “Functional nanomaterials and devices for biomedical sensing” in WiSE Program Women in Sensors

Staff involved: Minja Mladenović, Mirjana Mundžić, Aleksandra Pavlović, Ivana Podunavac, Nejra Omerović, Stefan Jarić, Mila Đisalov, Teodora Knežić, Dr. Nikola Knežević, Dr. Slavica Savić

Place: Online

Date: October 31 – November 4 2021

Website: <https://2021.ieee-sensorsconference.org/>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: IEEE Sensors 2021 Conference took place online as a live-streamed and interactive event on October 31 – November 4 2021. It has been organized by the IEEE Advancing Technology for Humanity and IEEE Sensors Council. A diverse set of globally renowned Keynote Speakers: Professor Justin Gooding from University of New South Wales (Sydney), Professor Debbie Senesky from Stanford University, and Professor Jérôme Casas from

University of Tours, France presented their work. In addition, a plenary session on Women in Sensors (WiSe) highlighted the contributions of some women leaders from our community. A broad combination of technical sessions – platform talks and poster sessions – presented in parallel each day, and had special sessions targeted for Young Professionals and Women in Sensors.

Since our group research focuses on the development of nanostructured silica-based biosensors for anticancer application, this conference was a perfect platform for gaining new knowledge. Furthermore, the conference provided first-hand information about current best practices in the field referred to above.

5. IEEE Authorship and Open Access Symposium: Best Practices to Get Published to Increase the Exposure and Impact of Your Research

Figure 38: NANOFACTS researchers at IEEE Symposium

Staff involved: Nejra Omerović, Ivana Podunavac, Mirjana Mundžić, Minja Mladenović

Place: Online

Date: 29 September 2021

Website:

https://event.on24.com/eventRegistration/EventLobbyServletV2?target=reg20V2.jsp&eventid=3036058&sessionid=1&key=A7A65D2E537E8E9592EB989C14727290&groupId=2125428&partnerref=LG_WBNR_4.2021_RFW_How_to_Publish_Open_Access_with_IEEE_Sales&sourcepage=register

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: The IEEE Authorship and Open Access Symposium took place online as a live streamed on the 29th of September 2021. This live webinar provided attendees with best practices in preparing a manuscript, navigating the journal submission process, and important tips to help an author get published. It also reviewed the opportunities for authors to enhance the visibility and impact of their research by publishing in the many open access options available from IEEE. Each informative session was featuring the perspective of distinguished author, editor, and professor Josep Guerrero from Aalborg University in Denmark, who provided critical insights on IEEE's peer review and submission processes and provided tips on what editors look for in submissions.

This webinar was excellent platform for our young researchers to gain knowledge and complete information about the rules and procedures in the publishing process, as well as their ability to choose the proper journal in order to increase the impact of the research and have the research results visible to the wide scientific audience.

6. XXIX International Materials Research Congress (IMRC2021)

Staff involved: Dr. Amelia Ultimo, Dr. Eduardo Ruiz-Hernandez

Place: Online

Date: 15 – 20 August 2021

Website: <https://www.mrs-mexico.org.mx/imrc2021/>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: The Sociedad Mexicana de Materiales and the Materials Research Society® organised the XXIX International Materials Research Congress. The conference offered a series of symposia on a variety of topics of interest to the broad materials research community as a whole. Four distinguished researchers participated in the congress as plenary speakers: Marie-Paule Pileni (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, France), Maurizio Prato (University of Trieste, Italy), Anke Weidenkaff (Fraunhofer Research Institution Materials Recycling and Resource Strategies, Germany) and Susanne Stemmer (University of California, USA). Dr. Ultimo took part in the Nanomaterials for Drug Delivery, Imaging and Immuno-Engineering Symposium as an invited speaker, with an oral contribution entitled “Mesoporous silica nanoparticles based therapeutic approaches”. This Symposium was co-organized and moderated by Dr. Eduardo Ruiz-Hernandez.

7. 5th International Caparica Symposium on Nanoparticles/Nanomaterials and Applications 2022 (ISN2A2022)

Figure 39: Dr. Amelia Ultimo at ISN2A2022

Staff involved: Dr. Amelia Ultimo, Dr. Maria Santos-Martinez, Dr. Eduardo Ruiz-Hernandez

Place: Caparica, Portugal

Date: 24 – 27 January 2022

Website: <https://www.isn2a2022.com/>

Goal: Dissemination and communication

Brief report: The ISN2A2022, organized by Bioscope in a hybrid edition, brought together about a hundred researchers in attendance in addition to a few dozen online participants. Six plenary talks have been offered during the congress, by esteemed professors engaged in research in the field of nanomaterials and their different possibilities of application: Thomas Webster (Northeastern University, Boston, USA), Ramon Martinez Mañez (Polytechnical University of Valencia, Spain), Sara E. Skrabalak (Indiana University Bloomington, USA), Laurent Boneviot (ENS Lyon, France), Isabel Pastoriza-Santos (University of Vigo, CINBIO, Spain) and Colin P. Nuckolls (Columbia University, USA). Dr. Ultimo participated with an oral contribution entitled “Combination anti-tumour

approach based on oligonucleotide-loaded exosomes and stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanocarriers”. The TCD team also contributed with two shot-gun presentations on “Functionalization and targeting of mesoporous silica nanoparticles for glioblastoma therapy” and “Mesoporous silica nanocarriers for sustained drug delivery in the treatment of lung cancer”.

3. Future activities and strategy

Future dissemination activities would include:

1. stronger engagement with partner institutions in social media posting
2. boosting the activities on social media platforms and creating new original content
3. Creating opportunities for dissemination of activities through newspaper, TV and radio appearances
4. Dissemination of activities through printed materials (brochures, leaflets etc.)
5. Further participation at scientific conferences and presentation of scientific results achieved through NANOFACTS activities
6. Publication of scientific articles in open access journals of large importance in the scientific community.

We plan to continue publishing news about project activities on the website and through social media. The main dissemination event (Training school) is planned for July 2022, which will offer significant possibilities for dissemination to a large number and diverse audience. We plan to advertise this event through different printed, electronic and news media. The plan is also to invite well known scientists as speakers during this event, which would disseminate NANOFACTS agenda to the audience. This event would also create significant opportunities for scientific networking through face-to-face communication among scientists of different backgrounds, between scientists and industry representatives, as well as the dissemination activities to students, general public and patients.